

**DRAMA AS CATALYST FOR RE-ENGINEERING THE YOUTH
AGAINST TERRORISM: MUSA SALIFU'S *THE REBEL SOLDIERS* AND
ALEX ASIGBO'S
THE REIGN OF PASCHAL AMUSU AS PARADIGM**

Ikechukwu O. EJELONU
Theatre Arts Department
Imo State University, Owerri.
Oluwa36@yahoo.com
ORCID No: 0000-0001-9409-0753

&

Gloria ERNEST-SAMUEL
Theatre Arts Department
Imo State University, Owerri.
gloimsu@yahoo.com
ORCID:0000-0001-5066-8998

Abstract

The high level of terrorism in the society is so alarming, as it has affected almost every aspect of life. It has caused a lot of havoc to both the lives of the people and the economic development of the society. It is a worrisome fact as the youths are mostly used as human tools to perpetrate such evil acts of violence and destruction. Therefore, this paper looks at the importance of drama/play texts, as vital means of re-engineering the mind and thoughts of the youths against terrorism using Musa Salifu's *The Rebel Soldiers* and Alex Asigbo's *The Reign of Paschal Amusu* for illustrative studies. The paper relied on Albert Bandora's Social Learning Theory. This paper makes use of textual analysis methodology in achieving its aim. The work finds out that through the playwrights' creative works/plays, certain acts of terrorism and socio-political issues and problems can be exposed, addressed, and resolved without violence. It recommends that more dramatic play texts exposing the dangers of violence and re-educating the youths on terrorism eradication be encouraged at all level of educational sector and the society at large.

Keywords: Drama, Terrorism, *The Rebel Soldiers*, *The Reign of Paschal Amusu*

Résumé

Le niveau élevé du terrorisme dans la société est si alarmant, car il a affecté presque tous les aspects de la vie. Cela a causé beaucoup de problèmes dans la vie de la population et dans le développement économique de la société. C'est inquiétant parce que les jeunes sont principalement utilisés comme outils humains pour perpétrer de tels actes pervers de violence et de destruction. Par conséquent, cet article se porte sur l'importance des textes dramatiques / pièces de théâtre comme moyens essentiels de réorientation de l'esprit et des pensées des jeunes contre le terrorisme en utilisant *The Rebel Soldiers* de Musa Salifu et *The Reign of Paschal Amusu* d'Alex Asigbo. L'article s'appuyait sur la théorie de l'apprentissage social d'Albert Bandura et la méthodologie de l'analyse textuelle pour atteindre son objectif. Le résultat montre qu'à travers les œuvres / pièces de théâtre des auteurs dramatiques, certains actes de terrorisme et questions sociopolitiques peuvent être soulevés, abordés et résolus sans violence. Il recommande que des textes plus dramatiques / pièces de théâtre exposant les dangers de la violence du terrorisme soient encouragés à tous les niveaux du secteur de l'éducation et de la société dans son ensemble afin de pouvoir éradiquer ce fléau.

Mots clés: Textes dramatiques, terrorisme, *The rebel soldiers*, *the reign of Paschal Amusu*

Introduction:

Drama like any other work of art, is a perceptive form that expresses the nature of human feeling, the rhythms and connections, crises and breaks, the complexity and richness of what is sometimes called man's inner life; the stream of direct experience, life as it feels to the living. It differs from other art forms because of its attribute of imitation. The existence of drama depends on its ability to reflect the transitions that characterize human society and also educate the people. The importance of drama in human society is quite enormous and culture specific. Drama has been a means of honouring the gods, pushing propaganda, debating controversial issues, remembering important people and events.

Theatre for education through drama has strong impact on learning and it's necessary because Enekwe opines that "Drama has been an instrument of socialization and cultural validation, drama is used to address issues that touch the whole community and to ensure that the messages are understood and internalized by the members of the community" (7).

Drama aids knowledge and educational development as it helps students to develop the ability to visualize events, learn the art of decision making, skills of interpretation, respect for divergent views, as well as engage in creative thinking.

According to Nobert Eze, “it is the quickest and surest means of stimulating the senses and engendering attachment to the object of study. It facilitates understanding and makes rendition easy since children takes lessons from a participatory position” (39). Drama can be used to soften passions of sorrow and anxiety thereby enabling the spectators to escape momentarily the worries of mundane existence and foster peace and socio-political stability. Drama concerns itself ostensibly with public and social morality, especially with good government, universal justice and individual worth or value as well as national order. Despite many challenges such as political instability, economic recession, social stratification, terrorism, kidnapping, schismatic as orchestrated by leadership ineptitude that threaten development, the Theatre Artist/Playwright as an interventionist and a mouth piece of the people has stood firm to correct and avert the cataclysm and regrettable ruin that the country is vulnerable to through the effective use of drama.

Conflict is a natural aspect of the human society and may arise from the pursuit of divergent interests, goals and aspirations by different individuals or groups in defined social and physical environments. According to Chinyere Lilian Okam, "This is because our lives rotate around pursuits which oscillate between different interests making us create threats that could affect others in the society"(55). However, the devastating effects of conflict are such that choosing it would have been a last resort but for the ignorance that has characterized the populace, especially the youth. One major source of conflict and war in this contemporary period is from terrorism and activities of terrorist groups. All over the world, there has been an increase in young groups that resort to unconventional tactics of traditional warfare. This has caused worrisome destruction of lives and properties in various societies and has greatly affected the economic development of the environment. According to Oparah C., “terrorism can be described as the wrongful use of violence in order to intimidate civilians or politicians for ideological, religious or political reasons with no regard for public safety” (165). In recent years, government and ordinary people have paid much more attention to terrorism than ever before. But terrorism itself is not new. Terrorism is basically just another step along the spectrum of violence leverage from conflict and war. According to Glodstein & Pevehouse, they opine that “terrorism refers to political violence that targets civilians deliberately and indiscriminately” (145). Beyond this basic definition other criteria can be applied. Terrorism is a shadowy world of faceless enemies and irregular tactics marked by extreme brutality.

Generally, the purpose of terrorism is to demoralize a civilian population in order to use its discontent as leverage on national, government or other parties to a conflict. Some terrorist groups aim at creating destructive “drama” in order to

gain media attention for a course. The primary effort of terrorism is psychological. In part, the effectiveness of terrorism in capturing attention is due to the dramatic nature of the incidents, especially as established by television news and newspaper. Terrorism also gains attention because of the randomness of victims. Although only a few dozen people may be injured by a bomb left in a market, millions of people realized “it could have been me” because they too shop in markets. Terrorism thus amplifies a small amount of power by its psychological effect on large population, this is why it is a tool of the powerless. The psychological impact of terrorism is even stronger than the physical damage. In Nigeria, the issues and problems of terrorism have come from activities of the Niger Delta militants, Fulani herdsmen and Boko Haram group. Looking at the issue of Boko Haram, its foundation is laid on the belief and practices on Islamic extremism. Khusamat, states that,

In 1995, some Muslim youths came together under the co-ordination of Mallam Lawal to form what they called Shabaab Muslim Youth Organization (S.M.Y.O). In 2001, the name of the groups changed to Jama’atu a Sunnah Hlis Ladda’ Awatih Wal-Jihad, translated in English to mean people committed to the propagation of the prophet’s teaching and Jihad (66).

He further states that “The name Boko Haram is the Hausa name – a kind of alias or appendage given to the Organization. It means western education is sinful” (67).

The leader Mohammed Yusuf was a graduate of education. He was described as an intelligent man with a touch of Western education and culture. However, his leadership of Boko Haram stood firm against any form of interaction with the Western world or science. The group also believed it could change the current system of education in Nigeria from western to Islamic form of education. The group also thought it can obstruct democracy and eradicate Christianity in northern Nigeria. The leader Mohammed Yusuf died in 2009 during a confrontation with Nigeria military forces and a new leadership in the name Abubakar Shekau emerged.

The organization had carried out series of assassinations, murders, jailbreaks, random and coordinated bombings. Among them is the bombing of the Abuja Police Headquarters in 2011, suicide bombing at army headquarters in Kaduna, bombing of several churches and above all bombing of a lecture theatre used for Christian worshiping at Bayero University campus, Kano were many students and lecturers died. The activities of terrorism by this group (Boko Haram) unsettled Northern Nigeria and directly or indirectly threatened the organization

of fruitful educational activities in the region. According to the National Bureau of Statistics (2015) Nigeria has spent over N3.6 trillion trying to contend with the insurgents in addition to scores of military and civilian lives lost as well as thousands of citizens confined to various camps as Internally Displace Persons (IDP). It is important to note that most of the attackers are young boys and girls who can use their time for better and meaningful endeavours. Thus, the need to enlighten the society especially the younger generation through various means of communication on the danger and effect of unlawful use of force and violence against persons or properties.

Oparah, submits that “terrorism combines fear, violence and intimidation to instill terror into their victims, it marks out defenceless target and attacks them to cause the government to give in to their demands that are most times so outrageous and impracticable” (168). Terrorism can be classified in many specific ways depending on which way you view the situation, the country and laws under which the attacks happen,

Some of the types of terrorism include:

Political terrorism: This involves terrorism geared towards gaining or manipulating political points. It relies on acts of violence to induce change in public opinion. Terrorists carry out attacks to bring people who accept their ideology or are willing to negotiate reasonably into power. Political terrorism can also be ethnically, politically or ideologically driven.

Non- political terrorism: This type of terrorism challenged towards non-political motives. It seeks to create the same atmosphere of fear and vulnerability political terrorism does, only that it does not seek to manipulate political events.

Quasi terrorism: it is a kind of emergency act of terrorism. In the case, the perpetrators use it to commit crime and produce the expected reactions and results. A typical example is a robbery committed while using hostage as leverage.

Religious terrorism: This terrorism carried out in the name or under the banner of religion or religious concept. The world labels this as religious extremism, going past conventional means to propagate your religious views and ideas.

State sponsored terrorism: This is terrorism financed and propagated by a sovereign state against itself own citizens or against citizens of other state. This is done as a method of pursuing foreign political objectives or to achieve their selfish goals or desires.

Terrorist groups employ wide range strategies to achieve their goal which is mainly to strike fear into the populace thereby leaving the government no choice than to agree to their term. Some of the methods they employ include: bombing, hostage taking, abduction, school killings, illegitimate governments, political assassinations, poisons and biochemical attacks and religious based attacks.

In order to counter this situation therefore, a creative writer must be ready to act not only as an interventionist, but as a conscience of his people. Through his communicative ability, he should persistently question and criticize the morals, attitudes, actions and inaction, myths and realities of his society so as to effect change and stability. It is based on this backdrop that this paper seeks to look at dramatic works as means of re-engineering the youth against terrorism. The playwright uses his creative works as a medium in re-enacting some prevailing realities in a bid to instigate positive change in the society as established in *The Rebel Solider* by Musa Salifu.

Theoretical Framework

Albert Bandura's Social Learning Theory is the trust of this work. Bandura, in Uwazurike opines that "individuals learn through observation, listening to other people, radio & television, reading, watching and action" (45). All these are models that influence human beings, therefore social learning theory looks at how these models influence the overall perception and behaviour of the individual. This social learning theory creates an environment where people acquire knowledge and information almost unconsciously. Bandura as the creator of this concept proposes five (5) essential steps in order for this theory to work effectively. They include observation, attention, retention, reproduction and motivation. This theory added a social element arguing that people can learn new ideas, information, and correct behaviours by observing, reading and imitating the behaviours of others. This shows that if a person perceives that there is a meaningful reward for such behaviour, they will emulate it at some point in the future. The researcher relies on this in relating it with the paper as it is necessary for the society to be enlightened or re-educated through drama. Such process enables the people to pay more attention to similar issues/situations, observe and reproduce positive attitude through effective motivations from the exposures, revelations, awareness impacts of dramatic literature. This further strengthens the need to recreate awareness, alertness and a great sense of peace and unity in the society through dramatic works. Furthermore, according to Khusamat, "exposure to and assimilation of new culture reform us and make us become functional instruments of change in the advancement of our society" (39). The theory aids youth to be cultural oriented and mould their instincts and behaviour so much that they become equipped with universal attribute or characteristics that can make them fit into the society they belong.

Dramatic Works as Re-Engineering Tool against Terrorism

Over the years, dramatic works have been used to creatively investigate facts and resolve issues. Such issues sometimes may relate to political, economic, cultural or social conflict in a given environment. Human beings tend to become more open minded, realistic rather than idealistic as they get exposed to certain issues. Hence the playwright's ability to create awareness is a vital key for positive change in a society. Atanda observes that "playwright guide the younger generation on social rules that specify appropriate and inappropriate behaviour in a given situation" (48). Dramatic works provide a framework of right and wrong perceptions and attitude expectations. Playwrights through their creative ability develop the works, with the intent to expose and correct the ills in the society. They point at the way forward for an equitable resolution of issues and project peaceful co-existence of people living in a certain geographical location. Furthermore, this unique means of communication through its ability to reach out to the inner mind of the people, aids to re-engineer, re-educate and re-position the society on possible ways to foster peace, harmonious inter-relationship and progress. Dramatic works, since they are inevitable to human existence touch almost every aspect of human life. They help to throw more light on the dangers and negative effects of such disorganizing situations like terrorism on the people. Dramatic works serve as a mirror through which the society reflects on resolving issues and situations. According to Soyinka in Atanda, "No matter under any disguise of suppression, oppressions, censorship or by the imposition of secular and theocratic ideologies, a writer's voice must not be silent" (45).

Looking critically at the dialogue in the play, especially as it relates to Tom David and Professor Samuel, one can say that it pushes for conflict management, and fosters the process of reducing the negative and destructive capacity of war/conflict through awareness and corrective measures. It revolves around how to handle conflicts positively without violence and points at efforts to be made to resolve conflict situations in our society. The aim of the dialogue as established in the play is to transform the mind, perceptions and attitudes of those involved in the conflicts. This is for them to mend their relationships, and the conditions that created the war or conflict situation. At the personal level, it involves emotional and perceptual aspects of change desired for an individual to emulate.

Furthermore, effective dialogue strengthened the themes of the plays which range from excessive ambition, poor leadership and corruption as established in the two texts used for this study. *The Rebel Soldiers* and *The Reign of Paschal Amusu* creatively through the dialogues used established allusions to the cause of the political instability and conflicts.

For example, in the play *The Rebel Soldiers*, Professor Samuel and Tom David serve as a foil that reveals the secrets of the conflict situations that have been re-occurring in that given society.

The dialogues used by the playwrights serve as a code for easy communication and understanding, which is impactful and meaningful to the reader. This dialogues used conveys meaning, feeling and related to life experiences that can be emulated from. Dramatic works through its creative communicative process simply re-engineers the mind on positive reasoning and change, which aids in sudden reverse of negative thoughts. Thus a playwright writes for or against any subject matter he set to discuss in his play depending on his stand point and perception of the issues under discuss. It is very necessary to point out that dramatic works use imitation and impersonation to speak to the audience mind which is clearly what Musa Salifu's *The Rebel Solider* and Alex Asigbo's *The Rebel Soldiers* represent.

Playwright like Zulu Sofola, Wole Soyinka and a host of others have through their works in one way or the other made remarkable contributions to the growth, stability and development of Nigeria using their creative proficiency and imagination to explore the social, political economic, cultural situations of the society.

The researchers made use of textual analysis methodology which will focus on the diction as it relates to the characters in the plays under study. It enlightens on the ability of the dictions used, to re-engineer and conscientize people's minds and attitudes towards positive change and social stability. This further proves the ability and effectiveness of dramatic works in changing people's perception and attitude towards the right directions, which will help the society, seek for proper strategies for conflict resolutions, peace, stability, and development in all ramifications. The researchers used this method in order to establish that Alex Asigbo and Musa Salifu used their dramatic works to poke the society's consciousness and to get them deeply involved in the logic of the plays. This is in order to push for a positive change of attitude and effectively foster more tolerance, unity and understanding within our environment. The plays used for this paper gear towards igniting revolutionary actions among the people by expressing the need for a psychological revolution among the oppressed masses and the manipulated youths.

Synopsis of the Play *The Rebel Soldiers*

The play "*The Rebel Soldiers*" is used by Musa Salifu to create awareness on the dangers of war/conflict situations in our society. He tried to link the past violent/war incidents to the present conflict situations in Ogugwu Kingdom. The play starts with a tense situation at a market in Republic of Omogwu, a group of

traders were selling different kinds of goods. Suddenly a huge bang disrupts the market as everyone struggles to safety, which gives a sense of worry and conflict situation. Immediately, the play reveals Adejo, Ele Ojo and Amodu discussing that all is not well, the rebel soldiers have again destroyed many properties and burnt more than a thousand people to death in Omogwu. In the play, the playwright creatively established a T.V programme 'The People Voice' anchored by Tom David while Professor Samuel from Federal University Omogwu is the guest speaker. These two characters' dialogue in the play was used by the writer to emphasize on the disadvantages of war, assassinations, unprovoked destruction of properties and massive human loss that is associated with socio-political conflicts situations. The characters were used by the playwright to draw emotions and positive reasoning embracing peace and unity in the society. They deliberated on the topic of crime wave, its causes and how it could be curbed, as the activities of Mr. Mayor's boys (The Rebel Soldiers) have caused a lot of havoc to both lives and properties of Omogwu.

In the play, the use of flashback effectively helped to link the present war/conflict situations with the world of the past leadership tussle and conflict incident. It established that in the past, Idu a son of Ogugwu due to excessive ambition for power and authority led the attack that killed and removed Angwason from power. Warrior Onye, who ascended the throne after the incident was equally from Ogugwu kingdom. This caused the Angwa Warriors to plan retaliation on the people of Ogugwu. In revenge, warrior Onye a son of Ogugwu clan and the leader of the kingdom was assassinated. This instigated war. A junior warrior from Angwa clan was deliberately placed as the leader. The Ogugwu people equally became furious and it led to a brutal conflict/war. Many Ogugwu people living in Angwa and other parts of Omogwu, were attacked, humiliated, wounded, slaughtered, massacred and few that managed to escape the war between the two clans became so horrible, which forced the Ogugwu people to surrender for peace. Warrior Hassan (the ruler) received and accepted with great empathy the plea for peace from Ogugwu clan and the war ended. The play points out the need for all to promote unity and fight with tireless effort against violence and terrorism. The play ends with Mayor and his boys facing the law for their unprovoked violent, crimes on defenseless people and society at large.

Synopsis of the play *The Reign of Paschal Amusu*

The play starts with a tense situation where Sasha who is the head of state is seen, where he caged Amusu, Shiwo and Dayo as political prisoners. He laments that he did not cancel Shiwo's election, that Masi (former ruler), Shiwo's friend did. Then why is it now under his leadership that Shiwo wants to take back his throne. He swears to deal with anybody who opposes him. As he bites a chunk off the

apple he is holding, a violent cough seizes him and he (Sasha) dies. At this political situation Masi and Salami (former leader) decide to support and give power to Paschal Amusu. Even though Salami do not trust Paschal Amusu, who he saw as a proud man and will not take kindly to being controlled from outside. Amusu approved the establishment of a bureau for financial crime Investigation as a potent weapon against perceived political opponents. He tried to manoeuvre his way for a third term agenda but failed and quickly he turned his focus on the job of his point man (Sony) as chairman of elders' committee of the ruling party. Due to much political irregularities, rigging, massive lobbying, selfishness and corrupt practices, there was a coup. The soldiers and masses revolted which made Amusu and his loyal servant Odibo to escape to the border, leaving only Sony his point man betrayed and dejected. The play creatively points at specific political situations in the country from Military regime, exposing the situations that led to change of power after the death of the former leader to the present civilian dispensation.

Impacts from the play *The Rebel Soldiers*.

The play: *The Rebel Soldiers* by Musa Salifu, paints a picture that reveals the negative impact of the terrorism on the society. The play relates similar past incidents with the present ones in order to enlighten and re-educate the mind on the dangers of terrorism and violence.

The playwright evolved a literary style that is unique in its committed presentation and representation of the human experiences. The play through its dialogue condemned the act of violence and terrorism, exposition of oppressive machinery and shared experiences of oppressive situation. The play exposed the obvious lack of unity and endemic internal conflict that exist among societies, which are major hindrances to collective unity, development and socio-political stability in any society. The play firmly encouraged the younger generation to fight against being used as tools of violence and terrorism, but rather pursue the common goal of peace, progress and socio-political harmony.

In x-raying the potency of dramatic works in re-shaping the mind and thoughts of the society, it is important to point that the play *The Rebel Soldier*, served as a means of enlightenment on the positive need for social development and stability which is key to the survival of the society. In the play, M.C De Great, while presenting a song on the T.V programme 'The People Voice', reflected on the present predicaments being faced by people. He sings; for them to throw away their guns for a better tomorrow and lasting peace established here:

MC De Great :We used to love one another We used to stand by one another. But today We kill one another, cause pains for one another. Oh yeah, things are not the same any more Please Let's listen to the crying voice of our injured brother and sisters. Please, let's listen to the lamentation of our wounded childrenPlease, carrier of death Throw away your guns Throw away your bombsCosWe all need peace todayLike yesterday For a better tomorrow So, Let's lift up our flags The flag,of peace! (7-8).

The character of M.C De Great, aims at re-engineering the mind of the youths towards a positive direction and change, as it relates to fighting terrorism and achieving unity. Perhaps it is clear that based on Salifu's characterization in the play, he attempts to create a mental picture of the nation's conflict situations. Also it is important to note that the thematic pre-occupation play is not centered on socio-political conflict alone but reflects on other themes. As a literary device, theme is the central topic or idea explored in a text. It is a pivotal element, because it lingers throughout the entire story, from start to finish. It is the underlying message that the writer would like to get across. Thus Musa, revolved around other important themes like, corrupt governance excessive ambition, and poor leadership, as he portrays leadership struggle, social discord, violence, and tragedy which are all offshoots of the restiveness we see today in our society. The play *The Rebel Soldiers* graphically presents the tension and destructive conflict in our society. In the play these other themes established, point at or reflect the ideological categories of the actions in the play, which gives meaning to the issues of socio-political conflict at stake. And further pushes for change of human attitude and conduct towards violence and terrorism. These themes in the play reflect in the characters' actions, setting and plot/events that makeup the story, and further stress frustrations or other disturbing issues faced by the communities that must reach a resolution.

Also, it is important to note that the thematic pre-occupation of the play is not the socio-political conflict alone. As a literary device, theme is the central idea explored in a text. It is a pivotal element, because it lingers throughout the entire story, from start to finish. It is the underlying message that the writer would like to get across. Thus, this story brings forth other important themes like excessive ambition, corrupt governance and poor leadership as he portrays leadership struggle, discord, violence and tragedy which are all off shoots of the restive we see today in the society in general. The play *The Rebel Soldiers* presents the high ideological tension and destructive conflict that have ruined our peaceful environment. It also pushes for change of attitude and conduct towards

terrorism and violence. The motive of these themes in the play, reflects in the character, actions, setting and plots that make up the story.

Furthermore, with the growth and demand of society on the issues of socio-political stability and peaceful co-existence, with the complexities and individual differences being sharper and more controversial, with various factors affecting today's life, it is necessary for dramatic works to reflect, criticize and air views which will fasten positive social change and awareness, which the play (*The Rebel Soldiers*) stands for. Such plays aid to fashion our attitude towards other people, it influences social-inter relationship and life in general.

Thus, effective communication and awareness through dramatic works can be imaginative so as to touch the reader's mind. According to Osofisan, creative artists heal the wounds of the mind:

The artist, and particularly the theatre artists, is most relevant for the artist is the great surgeon of the mind. I am saying that we can repair our historical blight, reestablish a belief in ourselves, create a new and positive identity, become controller of our own future if we allow the artists a central place, hence forth in all our strategies of planning (45-46).

Dramatic works like *The Rebel Soldiers* effectively serve as a tool for man to promote, propagate and preserve the total way of life; it teaches moral standards and pass vital information from one generation to the next.

According to Doki, "if the theatre is to have relevance in society it must not only be accessible but should also reflect the lives of the people. In other words, the theatre should be people oriented" (58). Obviously, this is established in the play as the television interactive programme was basically people oriented. The programme (*The People Voice*) was designed to expose re-enlighten and re-engineering the younger generation against terrorism and social ills. It points at the high level of fear, displacement, disorder and underdevelopment associated with such terrorism situation as showcased here:

Tom David: Once again thank you very much Prof (pauses and looks at his piece of paper again) you see the activity of Mr. Major's boys in particular has already caused lot of people and the economic development of our land (pauses) many lives have gone properties worth millions amount money have been destroyed even as I am talking to you Prof., we cannot close.

Professor Samuel: You are right (11).

It is important to make reference to the character of “Professor Samuel” in the play *The Rebel Soldiers* as an eye opener to the society. He exposes the causes of the re-occurring issues of socio-political situations of violence, leadership struggle and excessive ambition. These leads to unprovoked murder, social instability, destruction of properties and discord in the society. the character Professor Samuel established all this issues by reflecting the ugly incidents that happened in the past that led to assassination and war to the present socio-political violence, to the present socio-political violent situation in the play as he established here !!

Tom David: ...please Prof --- what happened after that ugly incident?

Prof Samuel: like I have said earlier, a mere junior warrior from Angwa kingdom, after the assassination of the son of Ogugwu took over the throne (Pauses and shakes his head) therefore, the people of ogugwu kingdom equally became sad and that and that, Mr. Presenter, led to a very terrible war... (30).

It is clear that Prof. Samuel, stressed on the irregularities that fueled the conflict situations, in order to further create public awareness and through such exposure and revelations, avoid future calamity and violence to re-occur again in that environment. As a symbol of peace in the play, Professor Samuel’s character always advocates for peace and unity as established here.

Tom David: please Prof. what do you think could be done to bring this problem to an end?

Prof Samuel: you see, if with the whole of our heart we take greed, injustice, tribalism and selfishness our worst enemies and wisely choose truth, justice, unity, selflessness and love as our true friends, Mr Presenter, believe you me our land will offer us nothing but a peaceful atmosphere (37).

Through Prof. Samuel’s character, the writer suggests that peace is key to social stability and progress in any given environment. Prof. Samuel emphasizes on peace and unity because he seems to hold the opinion that when everyone loves everyone, no one will want to inflict harm on the other. Therefore solutions other than war and bloodshed will be pursued with tenacity. It is important to note that systems of terrorism and oppression thrive in societies where extremism, poor leadership, excessive ambition of any kind, go unchecked. This play *The Rebel Soldiers* aims at correcting such negative attitudes. It points positively at the alternative ways to proffer peaceful solutions, foster social change and unity in a

society, which is what professor Samuel stands for in the play. These peaceful qualities he projected are in order to create social awareness and also to avoid re-occurrence of such ugly, inhuman and violent situations in the future.

Impacts from the play “*The Reign of Paschal Amusu*”

One major reason why terrorism continues in our society is that most Nigeria leaders, traditional and constitutional alike, emerge under very questionable circumstances. If any leadership is predicated on shaky foundations, as established in the play *The Reign of Paschal Amusu*, there are bound to be problems. Before now, in Nigeria’s political history, military juntas seized power through violence and coups d’etat without due regard for the will of the people or the rule of law. The situation has also been worrisome as it leads to more conflicts.

However, Asigbo’s revolutionary instinct is made manifest in his weaving of the final events of the play that inadvertently see to the overthrow of the powers that have held the society down for years. He creatively institutes a coup d’etat and erodes all Masi, Paschal Amusu and their band of political rogues who have placed the nation in tight situations that have caused misconceptions and conflicts. Asigbo used this technique to poke the audience critical consciousness and to get them consciously involved in the logic of the play as they unfold. In order to further enforce this, he introduces the characters one after the other and the characters when introduced take a bow before the audience. He employed this technique to perpetually detach the audience from getting emotionally attached to characters in the play. This is in order to further wear out the illusion of reality and taking cognizance of the dwindling fortune, in economy, peace and stability in the nation. The use of fictitious characters, the playwright rightly captured the events that occurred in Nigeria after the annulment of the 1993 general election which caused socio-political conflicts around the nation. He creatively exposed the machinations and intrigues of a cabal aimed at perpetuating themselves or their cronies in power at all cost. Tension builds in the country as Masi steps aside after setting up an interim government led by Sasha who later slumps and dies. Dramatist creatively made efforts to re-engineer and re-direct our conscience by exposing this evil acts and leadership issues through drama, so as to avoid such re-occurrence in the society. The intention of the playwright is to expose through dramatic works, the situations and persons directly involved in the traumatization and destruction of our economy which has hindered development and social stability. This is to sensitize the people to avoid such mistakes in the future, which may course aggressive, terrorism and conflicts.

The Reign of Paschal Amusu made it clear that unnecessary favouritism, diversion of national fund and interest to selected friends, cabal and tribe is the major causes of agitations, terrorism and political conflicts. Amusu admits releasing billions of naira for road construction which was diverted, yet he did not take any action.

Amusu: Eeen? Okay, tell me this, when I released billion to rehabilitate all the road in the country through you, what did do with the money

Sony: Well em.... You know.....

Amusu: No, no, no, answer me? It's not Sony Anita's fault abi? You messed me up a simple assignment and now (49).

Bad leadership and corruption instigate violence, as a leader, he knew that billions of the commonwealth has been diverted and projects approved by his government for the common good of the masses were not executed yet he kept quiet, enjoying himself while continuously plotting to remain in power for life. In the same vein the dramatist points at the level of corruption, as he established in play where Amusu, a sitting president, encourages bribery of the judges to pervert justice,

Odibo: I'm finished

Amusu: Who finished you?

Odibo: The courts...

Amusu: The courts? You're not making sense. What about the courts?

Odibo: They have just nullified my election

Amusu: What? You can't be serious..... I mean didn't you give the money?

Odibo: I did Sir, I did. Three hundred million, each of them (46/47).

Thus, in the abundance of commonwealth, the leaders, did little to improve the development of the country even after realizing that all the infrastructures have

degenerated. Rather, they embezzle the public fund on irrelevant issues and selfish interests, and turn the people against each other as they sponsor terrorism and violence in the society as established here;

Amusu: Send the presidential jet to Pitakwa immediately. Arrange to have their leader Esuene Wariboko brought here. We need to have a heart to heart with him.

Sony: At once my President!

Amusu: Offer him anything, as long as the step up their terrorism during the elections

Sony: I'll do that Sir!

Amusu: Of course you know we have to arrest him later. We must keep up appearances and reassure our foreign partners of our determination to end this insurgency (23).

Thus, this shows that the leaders sometimes are directly or indirectly involved with sponsoring terrorism and violence. This drama exposes the shortsightedness of our leaders, corruption, selfishness and issues leading to political conflict and terrorism. The playwright also succeeded in putting the leaders and the society at alert as to strive to avoid those pitfalls while pursuing good governance and peaceful co-existence in our environments.

Recommendations

- It is recommended that revelations, awareness and information in such places should serve as a clarion call on all future leader to jettison the idea of hiding at the back of godfatherism or corrupt politicians in getting into positions of power and authority, because they cannot serve the masses better under such negative cabal influences which most times leads to major conflicts.
- Contemporary dramatists should give more priority to the issues of peaceful conflict resolutions, national unity and integrational interest through the dramatic impacts embellished in the creative dictions and characterizations of their plays.
- The researchers recommend that the society and government of the day should not see drama as mere entertainment material but rather encourage dramatist to express their minds without fear, so as to put the leaders and the masses at alert in order to avoid reoccurrence of such destructive

conducts that causes destruction of lives and properties and hinders development in the society.

Conclusion

It is crystal clear that in order to ensure a peaceful co-existence and progress in any society, the playwrights have before them the task of discouraging such negative issues as ethnicity, dictatorship in leadership and other vices. They have the role of re-creating the possibilities of change and also channel the mind towards positive results and violence free society. Therefore, dramatic works with good qualities should be encouraged for an aggressive campaign against terrorism in the society.

Terrorism often linked to leadership failure in Nigeria as it hinders effective acquisition and impedes the demonstration of right values in Nigeria. The leaders are usually a reflection of the character of the society and interplay of contending social and political forces. Nigeria has been grappling with the problems of excessive ambition, corruption and poor governance in its polity for years. The reasons for its ugly continuous existence which often give room for terrorism attacks, are because it has become more of a culture. Also greed is deeply rooted in the life of the people, and lack of trust and truthfulness is a great challenge to peace, and unity. To exterminate these conflict issues, therefore, it becomes needful to re-orientate Nigerians about the positive values and conducts, which can bring about peace, stability and progress. Thus dramatists should use their creative works to promote values such as honesty, obedience, faithfulness, hospitality, and respect for laws, trust and many other right values in their society. This will aid to re-engineer the youth against violent behaviours and terrorism in the society, as established in the two plays used for this work.

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